

Title: Centrifuge modelling of suction anchors under multidirectional loading for shared mooring applications

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Abstract (150 – 200 words)

Shared anchors for floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) offer potential cost savings, but their geotechnical performance under complex multidirectional mooring loads in soft clay requires better understanding. To address this, centrifuge modelling was conducted at 75-g on model suction anchors in normally consolidated kaolin clay. The experiments simulated several loading scenarios, including monotonic pull-out and multidirectional loading patterns representing shared anchor configurations (three lines at 45° inclination to the horizontal plane, spaced by 120° azimuthally). Three load tests were performed: a monotonic reference test and two multidirectional tests involving alternating and simultaneous line loading. Measurements included the anchor load-displacement response and excess pore pressures with complementary data from digital image correlation. The baseline monotonic test yielded an ultimate capacity of approximately 4 MN. Alternating line loading induced progressive downward displacements, while simultaneous two-line loading produced a trend of upward movement. Simultaneous loading also led to greater horizontal displacements, reflecting increased mobilisation under compound loading paths. Post-multidirectional monotonic tests revealed reductions in anchor capacity between 10% and 38%, depending on the load path history and inclination. This work delivers benchmark data clarifying suction anchor behaviour under multidirectional loads, to validate numerical models and optimize shared anchor designs for FOWTs.

Keywords

Offshore renewable energy; Centrifuge modelling; Geotechnical engineering

List of notations

σ'_v	is the vertical effective stress
γ'	is the effective unit weight of the soil
D	is the diameter of the anchor
L	is the length of the anchor
T	is the anchor wall thickness
W	is the weight of the anchor
F	is the load applied to the anchor
$F_{ult,1}$	is the baseline capacity of anchor 1
$F/F_{ult,1}$	is the normalised load with respect to baseline capacity
s_u	is the undrained shear strength of the clay
N_t	is the t-bar factor for undrained shear strength calculation
N	is the centrifuge scale factor
g	is the earth's gravity acceleration
t	is the time recorded during the centrifuge tests
d	is the displacement of the anchor
β	is the inclination angle of the load applied at the anchor padeye

- θ is the anchor rotation angle
- H_{ult} is the estimated horizontal load capacity of the anchor at the optimal depth
- V_{ult} is the estimated ultimate vertical load capacity of the anchor
- ΔPwP is the change in excess pore pressure

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13 Introduction

14 The deployment of offshore wind energy infrastructure is expanding to meet renewable energy
15 targets, requiring installations in deeper waters (>60 m), where floating offshore wind turbines
16 (FOWTs) are necessary (Goupee et al., 2014). These turbines rely on effective mooring systems
17 anchored to the seabed to maintain stability under environmental forces (Jiang, 2025). Suction
18 caissons, constitute an anchoring solution for FOWTs, due to their relative installation efficiency,
19 silent installation, high holding capacity against combined loads arriving from floating structures
20 and versatility for installation in clay and sand seabeds (Cerfontaine et al., 2023; Coughlan et al.,
21 2025). Mooring systems contribute significantly to capital costs, accounting for approximately 10%
22 to 15% of total project expenses (James and Ros, 2015), driving efforts towards cost optimization.

23 To reduce costs and minimise the seabed footprint, the concept of 'shared anchors' or
24 'multiline anchors'- where a single anchor secures mooring lines from multiple FOWTs- is gaining
25 attention (Xu et al., 2024, Devin et al., 2021). Shared anchors decrease the number of required
26 foundations, reducing material use, installation time, vessel mobilization, and site investigations
27 (Lee and Aubeny, 2023; Fontana et al., 2018; Diaz et al., 2016). The operational feasibility of this
28 concept has been demonstrated in projects such as Hywind Tampen, where 19 suction anchors
29 were installed for an 11-FOWT farm (Ore Catapult and Arup, 2024; Sloan et al., 2022).
30 Furthermore, numerical simulations indicate that compared with single-turbine mooring
31 configurations, shared anchors can effectively mitigate peak horizontal loads, potentially
32 achieving reductions of up to 50% (Pillai et al., 2022; Fontana et al., 2018).

33 Despite increasing interest in shared anchors and their potential benefits, their
34 geotechnical behaviour under complex, multi-directional loading from multiple mooring lines
35 remains insufficiently understood. In particular, it is unclear whether anchor capacity increases,
36 decreases, or remains unchanged following cyclic loading. Anchor capacity is influenced by the
37 loading rate relative to the rate of pore pressure dissipation, which affects the mobilised shear
38 strength. Moreover, loading history can progressively alter the stress state and density of the
39 surrounding soil, further affecting the available strength. These processes can lead to capacity
40 changes—either reductions or gains—relative to the initial monotonic capacity, often by factors
41 ranging from 2--5 (Cerfontaine et al., 2023).

42 Some studies have reported capacity degradation due to cyclic loading. For example,
43 Chen and Randolph (2007) used centrifuge tests to investigate the uplift capacity of suction
44 anchors in normally consolidated clay under sustained and cyclic loading. They applied load
45 packages comprising 50 cycles with amplitudes between 50% and 90% of the monotonic
46 capacity, over prototype times ranging from 17--34 days, and observed a reduction in the holding
47 capacity to 72%--86% of the undrained monotonic capacity. Similarly, field tests by Dyvik et al.
48 (1993) revealed that the bearing capacity of suction anchors in clay under cyclic loading
49 decreased to approximately 66%--82% of the static capacity. Conversely, other studies have
50 reported capacity enhancement following cyclic loading. Lee et al. (2024) conducted centrifuge
51 experiments on suction anchors in soft clay under cyclic inclined pull-out loading and reported a
52 32% increase in postcyclic monotonic capacity. This gain was observed when the monotonic load
53 was applied immediately after the cyclic loading phase, indicating that reconsolidation was not
54 required for the strength increase. The concept of "whole-life changes" in capacity, as outlined by
55 Gourvenec (2020), emphasizes that cyclic loading, when combined with consolidation, can
56 increase the strength of soft clays. These changes in soil properties may result in increased
57 anchor capacity—an effect that is often overlooked in conventional design approaches.

58 A knowledge gap remains regarding the response of suction anchors embedded in soft,
59 normally consolidated clay under simultaneous loads from multiple mooring lines, which are
60 representative of shared anchor configurations. This study aims to address this gap by developing
61 and testing an experimental setup within the geotechnical centrifuge at Université Gustave Eiffel,
62 specifically designed to apply controlled, multidirectional loading to suction anchors. The
63 configuration allows up to three inclined loads to be applied simultaneously to a single suction
64 anchor, with mooring lines spaced 120° azimuthally and pulling at 45° to the horizontal plane. To
65 evaluate the setup's performance and reliability, three simplified monotonic load/unload paths
66 were applied. The anchor response was monitored via load cells on each mooring line to measure
67 the applied forces and determine the mobilised capacity. Overall anchor displacements were
68 recorded via laser displacement transducers. Additionally, pore pressure transducers were
69 embedded at the top and base of the anchors to measure the evolution of excess pore
70 pressures—particularly suction—during loading. The experimental results provide benchmark
71 data for validating numerical models and offer initial insights into anchor behaviour under

72 controlled multi-directional loading, forming the basis for future, more complex experimental
73 campaigns.

74 2. Experimental setup and model preparation

75 2.1 Description of the centrifuge tests

76 A series of loading tests was conducted on three suction anchors installed in normally
77 consolidated clay. The experiments utilized the 4.5-m-radius geotechnical centrifuge at the
78 Université Gustave Eiffel, Nantes campus (formerly LCPC and IFSTTAR) (Corte, 1984).

79 2.2. Sample preparation

80 Speswhite kaolin, which is a well-documented material extensively employed in centrifuge
81 modelling (Springman, 1993; Raines and Garnier, 2004; Thorel et al., 2011; Lau, 2015), was used
82 to build a normally consolidated clay profile. The clay sample was prepared by mixing kaolin with
83 water to achieve a water content of 90% before consolidation. The resulting slurry was then
84 poured into a cylindrical container (895 mm in diameter and 700 mm high), on a 90 mm thick base
85 drainage layer placed at the bottom of the container to facilitate consolidation of the clay. A total
86 amount of approximately 280 kg of kaolin clay was required to prepare the clay sample.

87 The clay profile was constructed in four layers, each subjected to a specific
88 preconsolidation pressure determined from a target effective vertical stress profile (assuming an
89 effective unit weight, $\gamma' = 6 \text{ kN/m}^3$). Consolidation was performed at 1-g using a computer-
90 controlled hydraulic press over a total period of one month, similarly to Khemakhem (2012). Figure
91 1 illustrates the target consolidation pressures for each sublayer and the resulting thickness of
92 the clay profile upon completion of consolidation.

93

94 Figure 1. Target pre-consolidation pressures to build a normally consolidated clay profile
95 (right axis in prototype scale)

96 **2.3 Experimental setup**

97 A prototype suction anchor with a diameter (D) of 4.5 m and a length (L) of 15.0 m, resulting in a
 98 length-to-diameter ratio (L/D) of 3.3, was selected to be comparable to the Hywind Tampen wind
 99 farm, where the shared anchor concept has been implemented (Coughlan et al., 2025). A
 100 centrifuge scaling factor of $N=75$ was adopted to enable the testing of three model suction anchors
 101 in one consolidated sample. Each anchor included three padeyes, positioned at approximately
 102 two-thirds of the anchor length from the top, to enable inclined load application from three mooring
 103 lines. Figure 2 presents a plan view of the anchor layout and a representation of the mooring line
 104 load application points ($L1$, $L2$, and $L3$). The center-to-center spacing between adjacent anchors
 105 is approximately $6.4D$, and the distance from each anchor center to the model container boundary
 106 is approximately $3.6D$. Table 1 summarizes the model and prototype dimensions. An overview of
 107 centrifuge scaling laws used in the tests is provided by Garnier et al. (2007).

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110

111

Figure 2. Plan view of the experimental setup: location of the suction anchors

Table 1. Prototype and model dimensions

	Dimension	Model (1/75)	Prototype
	Material	Aluminum	
	D, diameter	60.0 mm	4.5 m
	L, length	200.0 mm	15.0 m
Suction Anchor	L/D	3.3	3.3
	t (wall thickness)	0.4 mm	3.0 cm
	D/t	150.00	150
	W, weight	330.0 g	1.39 MN
	W', buoyant weight	277.2.0 g	1.14 MN
Model Container	Height	700 mm	52.5 m
	Diameter	895 mm	67.1 m
	Water table	50 mm	3.75 m
Clay sample	Thickness	350 mm	26.3 m

112

113 Figure 3 shows the experimental setup used in the centrifuge test. The setup included a
 114 combination of fixed components (parts No.1 to No. 7 in Figure 3b) designed to support the
 115 actuators, pulleys, cameras, and laser sensors, along with movable components such as the
 116 mooring lines and anchors. Three electric actuators (Figure 3a) were employed to apply the loads
 117 and were instrumented with load cells (TME cells with 5 kN capacity). An extension piece was
 118 attached to the top of the anchor (part No. 8), comprising an aluminium pipe and a circular cap
 119 fabricated using a 3D printer. This extension was designed to facilitate additional measurements
 120 of the anchor's rotations, vertical displacements, and translational movements. Although
 121 lightweight, the extension added a surcharge equivalent to 10% of the anchor's total weight.

122
 123 Figure 3. Experimental setup for multiline anchor testing. a) Perspective view of the model
 124 container and actuators. b) Detailed view of an anchor and instrumentation.

125
 126 A rotating assembly was developed to reduce the time between tests, by allowing the
 127 anchor testing location within the model container to be repositioned through rotation, while the
 128 container itself remained stationary. The data logging system (Quantum HBK multi IO) was
 129 integrated directly into this rotating assembly, which minimized the need for repeated
 130 disconnection and reconnection of sensor cables during the testing sequence. Figure 4 shows
 131 the position of the rotating assembly during the tests on anchor 1 and anchor 3 (Figure 2).

Figure 4. Rotating assembly to test various anchor locations

2.4 Suction anchor installation

The anchors were installed at 1-g by manually pushing them into the clay. While suction is used for offshore anchor installation, jacking or manual pushing at 1g is a suitable alternative in centrifuge modelling. Chen and Randolph (2007) reported no significant differences in axial capacity or radial stress changes between caissons installed by suction in-flight and those jacked at 1-g in normally consolidated clay. The installation depth corresponded to the full length of the anchors (200 mm). During this process, the top valves of the anchors were kept open to allow trapped air within the caisson to escape, as illustrated in Figure 5a and Figure 5c. To ensure vertical alignment during insertion, a guide constructed from an aluminium pipe was utilized; this guide could later be removed by unscrewing it from the anchor's top cap. The guide mechanism also incorporated a 3D-printed support piece (Figure 5b), which was attached to the main top plate (part No. 2 in Figure 3) to guarantee the verticality of the anchor during installation.

146

147 Figure 5. a) Detail of a model anchor; b) guide mechanism for installation; c) anchor installation
 148 at 1-g

149 During anchor installation, the mooring lines were manually pretensioned simultaneously
 150 to cut through the surrounding clay and ensure a consistent starting point for load application.
 151 This process established a uniform exit point at the clay surface for all three lines. Once this was
 152 achieved, the pretension was released. Figure 6 shows an anchor after 1g installation, including
 153 the footprint left by the mooring lines during pretensioning. To ensure correct alignment of the
 154 lines within the pulleys, 3D-printed components, referred to as stop cables, were used (part No.
 155 6 in Figure 2). The mooring lines were made of 4 mm diameter SK78 Dyneema synthetic ropes.
 156 These cables have a Young's modulus ranging from 108 GPa to 113 GPa (Vlasblom, 2018), a
 157 linear weight of approximately 9 g/m, and a load resistance of 1300 daN at 1% elongation (LIROS,
 158 2025).

159

160 Figure 6. A view of a model anchor and instrumentation after installation at 1-g

161 **2.5 Model Instrumentation**

162 The centrifuge model was instrumented as follows. Druck pore-pressure transducers (PPTs) were
 163 embedded during clay consolidation at three elevations: (i) one anchor diameter (1D) below the
 164 caisson base, (ii) at the caisson base, and (iii) at the caisson top (Figure 7a). The clay surface
 165 settlements were measured with LVDTs. Lateral displacements of the anchors were tracked using
 166 linear laser transducers (Baumer OM20), configured to detect the centre of cylindrical objects
 167 within their measurement field. By arranging two linear lasers perpendicularly, the movement of
 168 the anchor extension could be tracked in a x-y (horizontal) plane (Figure 7b). Additional Baumer
 169 OM20 point lasers were positioned above the model to measure vertical displacements at the top
 170 of the extension piece and estimate anchor rotations on the basis of their relative distance
 171 (Figure 7c).

172
 173 Figure 7. Model instrumentation. a) Lateral view of an anchor and connection of one mooring
 174 line. b) Linear lasers position to track lateral displacements. c) Point lasers to track vertical
 175 displacements and detail of an ArUco marker

176
 177 To obtain additional displacement data via digital image correlation (DIC), an ArUco
 178 marker (Garrido et al., 2014) was placed on the upper extension of the anchor (Figure 7c). A
 179 camera (IP network camera HDI-47) mounted above the anchors enabled tracking of the marker's

180 displacement, primarily within a planar projection. The tracking process was conducted using
181 Blender software, and the detailed procedure for performing these analyses was outlined by
182 Soriano et al. (2021).

183 **2.6. Centrifuge Testing Programme**

184 Three load tests were conducted: a monotonic test to establish the baseline anchor
185 capacity, followed by two multidirectional loading tests. The primary objective was to evaluate the
186 performance of the experimental setup using simplified load paths. Although these load paths do
187 not replicate specific offshore conditions, they serve as a proof of concept to demonstrate the
188 setup's ability to apply and monitor controlled multiline loading. This framework can later be
189 extended to incorporate cyclic and time-dependent loading scenarios. While the current tests do
190 not aim to fully characterise anchor behaviour, the results offer initial insights that may support
191 the calibration of numerical models and guide the design of future studies under more realistic
192 loading conditions. The testing conditions of the anchors are summarized in Table 2.

193
194

Table 2. Identification of loading tests for the suction anchors

Anchor	Load condition	Load rate (model scale)
1	Monotonic	30 mm/min
2	Multidirectional alternated	30 mm/min
3	Multidirectional two lines alternated	30 mm/min

195

196 The loading sequence varied for each anchor but maintained a consistent load inclination
197 of 45° to the horizontal. Anchor 1 was subjected to a monotonic inclined load applied by mooring
198 line L1 (Figure 3). This test established a baseline for the anchor capacity. Anchor 2 underwent a
199 series of monotonic loads applied alternately through lines L1, L2, and L3, each inclined at 45°.
200 The load amplitude progressively increased in successive cycles, as illustrated in Figure 8a. This
201 alternating sequence resulted in varying load components, which can be decomposed into three
202 orthogonal directions: x and y in the horizontal plane, and z in the vertical plane. Figure 8b shows
203 the evolution of these load components during a representative load cycle. For reference, the x-
204 axis was defined as the positive direction of the load applied to Line L1

205

206 Figure 8. Anchor 2: progressively increasing amplitude monotonic loads applied by alternating
 207 mooring lines
 208

209 Anchor 3 was tested under simultaneous loading from two mooring lines at a time, also
 210 inclined at 45° , alternating between line pairs (L1–L2, L2–L3, L1–L3). The load amplitude
 211 progressively increased in each pairwise sequence, as depicted in Figure 9a. The superposition
 212 of two inclined loads resulted in a resultant force with a steeper inclination than the individual line
 213 loads. Figure 9b provides a schematic representation of this combined loading and the calculation
 214 of the resultant force from a pair of forces.

215

216 Figure 9. Anchor 3: progressively increasing amplitude monotonic loads applied by two mooring
 217 lines simultaneously.

218 Note that Figure 8 and Figure 9 present the load sequences schematically, without
219 detailing the time intervals between load steps, for clarity.

220 **2.7 Test procedure**

221 Anchor testing was carried out over three days, with one test conducted per day. The
222 swing up of the model consisted of increments of 10-g until reaching the target acceleration level
223 for the test (75-g). Once at the target acceleration, the model was kept in flight for 5 hours. To
224 evaluate the in-situ soil strength conditions prior to each anchor test, a T-bar penetration test was
225 performed in-flight each day. These tests were conducted at a penetration rate of 2 mm/s using a
226 T-bar penetrometer with a diameter of 5 mm and a length of 20 mm, resulting in a projected area
227 of 100 mm².

228 The undrained shear strength profiles shown in Figure 10 were derived from data
229 recorded by a potentiometer attached to the T-bar actuator and force measurements from a load
230 cell positioned at the top of the T-bar. A T-bar factor $N_t=10.5$ was used in the calculations (Stewart
231 and Randolph, 1991). Only two profiles are shown due to sensor malfunction during the first test.
232 Additionally, after the centrifuge was stopped, hand shear vane tests were conducted at various
233 depths via a Pilcon vane tester with a 33 mm diameter and 50 mm blade length. This method,
234 which is commonly used in clay-based centrifuge studies (Divall et al., 2016; Panchal et al., 2020),
235 provides additional undrained strength data. The results from both methods indicate that the
236 strength profile increases with depth, from approximately 2.5 kPa at the surface to 10 kPa at the
237 anchor tip depth of 15 m. The close agreement between the vane and T-bar measurements
238 confirms their complementarity in characterizing the clay profile. A data sampling frequency of 10
239 Hz was used for monitoring the consolidation phase, whereas a higher frequency of 100 Hz was
240 employed during the anchor load tests and the T-bar tests.

241

242 Figure 10. Undrained shear strength profiles measured in-flight and 1-g shear hand vane tests

243

244 3. Test results

245 3.1 Monotonic load test – Anchor 1

246 The normalized load–displacement response of Anchor 1 is shown in Figure 11a. The
 247 load was measured using the actuator load cell, and the displacements corresponded to those
 248 imposed by the actuator. The load increased until it reached a plateau at $F_{1,ult} = 4$ MN, which was
 249 defined as the baseline capacity for subsequent multidirectional tests. Displacements were
 250 normalized by the anchor diameter D . To approximate the displacement at the loading depth
 251 (labelled d_{xz} in Figure 11a), a combination of laser measurements was used. One linear laser
 252 measured the lateral displacement (d_1), while point lasers were used to estimate the anchor's
 253 rotation (θ). The vertical displacement was estimated as the average of the vertical displacements
 254 recorded by the point lasers positioned at the top of the anchor extension (d_z). This combined
 255 approach allowed the construction of an approximate load–displacement curve at the load
 256 application depth. However, the accuracy was limited by the measurement range of the lasers.
 257 An offset was applied to this load-displacement curve to align its trend with the actuator-derived
 258 curve at approximately $0.2D$ normalized displacement. The difference between the actuator-
 259 imposed displacement and the response at the anchor load depth indicates that some initial
 260 actuator movement is required before effective load transfer to the anchor occurs. This may reflect
 261 slack in the system or interactions between the mooring line and surrounding clay that must be
 262 overcome before the anchor resists the load.

263

264 Figure 11. Anchor 1: load-displacement response and excess pore pressure measurements at
 265 the top and at the base of the anchor
 266

267 To facilitate a comparison of pore pressure responses, an initial offset was applied to the
 268 measured values, setting them to zero at the start of loading (ΔPwP in Figure 11b). During loading,
 269 both pore pressure transducers (PPTs) recorded decreasing values beginning near a normalized
 270 displacement of $0.2D$, indicating load transfer to the anchor. The development of these negative
 271 excess pore pressures indicates the progressive mobilisation of reverse end bearing capacity and
 272 confirms the effective sealing of the anchor's top cap.

273 After unloading, residual negative pore pressure remained inside the anchor. Conversely,
 274 at the base, the excess pore pressure became positive, likely because of anchor settlement during
 275 unloading, resulting in pressure build-up in the underlying soil.

276 **3.2. Multidirectional alternated load test – Anchor 2**

277 The force–displacement responses for each mooring line connected to Anchor 2 are
 278 shown in Figure 12. The loading sequence begins with Line 2, followed by Line 3, and concludes
 279 with Line 1. All forces are normalized by the monotonic capacity of Anchor 1 ($F_{1,ult} = 4 \text{ MN}$), and
 280 the displacements correspond to actuator-imposed values. While anchor displacements were
 281 also monitored, they are not shown here due to limitations in capturing full 3D movements and

282 the potential for laser sensor range exceedance at large displacements. Normalised actuator
 283 displacements are therefore used consistently across tests to enable comparison. Line 2, which
 284 was also the first to be loaded, was subjected to an additional cycle at the end of the sequence
 285 (Cycle 5), during which a monotonic load was applied until a plateau was reached at
 286 approximately 3.6 MN (0.9 $F/F_{1,ult}$). For reference, the load–displacement curve from the
 287 monotonic test on Anchor 1 is included in the figure. Across the load–unload cycles, a two-phase
 288 trend is observed: an initial concave slope up to a normalized displacement of approximately
 289 $0.2D$, followed by a change in stiffness. This transition is consistent with the behaviour noted in
 290 Anchor 1, where effective load transfer to the anchor appears to begin beyond this displacement
 291 threshold. Overall, the curves follow a backbone response pattern when compared with the
 292 monotonic loading of Anchor 1.

293
 294 Figure 12. Anchor 2: Load displacement curves for each mooring line

295
 296 Figure 13 shows the average vertical displacements of the anchor, measured by the
 297 lasers positioned at the top of the extension piece (Figure 7c), along with the applied actuator
 298 loads. During Cycle 1, no significant pullout displacement was observed, indicating that part of
 299 the applied load was mobilized before reaching the anchor, which is consistent with previous
 300 observations. From Cycle 2 onwards, progressive settlement of the anchor was recorded, with

301 increased displacements occurring primarily during the unloading phases. Overall, the amplitude
 302 of the vertical displacement loops correlates with the magnitude of the applied loads.

303
 304 Figure 13. Anchor 2: Relationship between applied load and average vertical displacements
 305

306 Figure 14a presents the time history of the loads applied to the anchor, demonstrating
 307 the consistent performance of the force control system throughout the test. Figure 14b shows the
 308 excess pore pressure measurements recorded at the top and base of the anchor. Both
 309 transducers exhibit similar trends during loading, with negative excess pore pressures (suction)
 310 developing in proportion to the applied load magnitude. The transducer at the base also shows a
 311 gradual increase in pore pressure over the test sequence, indicating a net buildup of positive
 312 pressure. This trend is attributed to the cumulative downwards movement (settlement) of the
 313 anchor under repeated load–unload cycles, as illustrated in Figure 14c.

314

315

316 Figure 14. Anchor 2: alternated monotonic load with increasing magnitude, excess pore
 317 pressures and vertical displacements response

318 3.3 Multidirectional alternated load by two simultaneous mooring lines test – Anchor 3

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Figure 15 shows the load–displacement curves for Anchor 3, where loads were applied simultaneously through two mooring lines. The results are presented in terms of the resultant force and displacement, as defined in Figure 9b. Although each mooring line was inclined at 45° to the horizontal, the combination of two inclined loads produced a resultant force with a higher average inclination of approximately 63° . Additionally, the normalized forces exceeded $F/F_{1,ult} = 1.0$ when referenced to the baseline capacity of Anchor 1. The load–displacement curves for the different mooring line pairs exhibit similar trends in stiffness and shape, although they differ from the response observed for Anchor 1. This deviation is likely due to the steeper load inclination in the bidirectional configuration. After the bidirectional loading sequence, a final monotonic pull was

329 applied through Line 2. In this case, a reduced anchor capacity was observed, reaching a plateau
 330 at a load of 2.5 MN, corresponding to $F/F_{1,ul} \approx 0.63$.

331
 332 Figure 15. Anchor 3: Resultant force- displacement curves for simultaneous loads applied by
 333 two mooring lines simultaneously
 334

335 Figure 16 summarizes the relationship between the resultant force components and the
 336 average vertical displacement of anchor 3. During the first three cycles, the anchor generally
 337 returned to its initial position after unloading, with relatively narrow load–unload loops indicating
 338 limited permanent deformation. In Cycle 4, however, larger upwards displacements were
 339 recorded, reaching approximately $0.4D$. This cycle exhibited a clear upwards trend, resulting in
 340 permanent vertical displacement in the pullout direction.

341

342 Figure 16. Anchor 2: Relationship between applied load and average vertical displacements

343

344 Figure 17a presents the resultant bidirectional forces applied during the test, showing
 345 consistent performance of the load control system across the defined load levels. The excess
 346 pore pressure responses measured at the anchor base and at a depth of one anchor diameter
 347 (1D) below the base are shown in Figure 17b and generally follow similar trends. Negative excess
 348 pore pressures developed during loading, with magnitudes proportional to the applied loads. An
 349 exception occurred during the final loading stage, which involved a monotonic pull applied to Line
 350 2. In this case, the pore pressure response was less pronounced, suggesting that prior
 351 bidirectional loading caused accumulated uplift displacements (Figure 17c), reducing the anchor's
 352 ability to mobilize significant suction pressures.

353

354 Figure 17. Anchor 3: alternated monotonic load by two simultaneous mooring lines with
 355 increasing magnitude, excess pore pressures and vertical displacements response
 356

357 3.4 Digital image correlation analysis

358 Figure 18 presents the trajectory of the marker positioned at the top of the anchor extension
 359 in the x-y (horizontal) plane for Anchors 2 and 3, which was obtained using Digital Image
 360 Correlation (DIC) and linear laser displacement sensors. As the laser sensors were positioned
 361 below the marker location, a geometric scale factor was applied to approximate the marker
 362 displacements from the laser data. It is important to note that these measurements do not
 363 represent displacements at the anchor top or at the load application point but rather at the location
 364 of the marker used for DIC validation. This setup was implemented to enable a qualitative
 365 comparison between the responses of Anchors 2 and 3 and can be extended to more complex
 366 load paths or other foundation types, such as monopiles.

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368 Figure 18. Trajectory of the ArUco marker, placed on the extension piece during anchor 2 and
 369 anchor 3 tests

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Owing to the limited range of the laser sensors, the full displacement path could not be captured during the later stages of the test. Nevertheless, within their operational range, the laser and DIC measurements show good agreement. Compared with Anchor 2, Anchor 3, subjected to simultaneous bidirectional loading, exhibited a wider range of horizontal displacement. This increased response is attributed to the combined effect of two inclined loads acting concurrently, resulting in greater mobilization of the anchor. The most significant displacement increments were observed during the final three load–unload cycles and the subsequent monotonic pull.

Finally, DIC measurements are limited to a two-dimensional projection in the x – y plane. As a result, the recorded displacements may include both translational and rotational components, which cannot be fully separated using the current single-camera configuration.

3.5 Anchor capacity evaluation using experimental results and analytical envelope

A finite element simulation of the anchor capacity was conducted using BIFURC (NGI, 1997) to estimate the lateral and vertical load capacities when loading was applied at a depth corresponding to two-thirds of the anchor length. On the basis of the undrained shear strength profile obtained from the T-bar tests (Figure 11), the ultimate lateral capacity was estimated as $H_{ult} = 3.1$ MN and the vertical capacity was $V_{ult} = 4.0$ MN. The failure envelope shown in Figure 19 was constructed using the analytical formulation proposed by Supachawarote et al. (2004)

388 (Equation 1), which accounts for normally consolidated clay with increasing undrained strength
 389 with depth.

$$\left(\frac{H}{H_{ult}}\right)^{\frac{L}{D}+0.5} + \left(\frac{V}{V_{ult}}\right)^{\frac{L}{3D}+4.5} = 1 \quad (1)$$

390

391 where L is the length of the anchor and D, is the anchor's diameter.

392

393 Figure 19. Horizontal-vertical (H-V) failure envelope with comparison to the load responses
 394 from Anchors 1 to 3

395 The results, presented in prototype scale units, show that the monotonic test on Anchor
 396 1 (load inclination $\beta = 45^\circ$) closely aligns with the estimated failure envelope. In contrast, the
 397 bidirectional load tests, with a combined load inclination of approximately $\beta = 63^\circ$, produced data
 398 points slightly above the failure envelope during the final load cycle. The shape of the failure
 399 envelope and the experimental data points suggest that, for the tested configuration and anchor
 400 geometry, the vertical load capacity exceeds the lateral capacity. The post-cyclic monotonic tests,
 401 also with a 45° load inclination, revealed a reduction in anchor capacity, highlighting the influence
 402 of prior loading history on anchor performance.

403 Conclusions

404 This study presented a centrifuge testing programme aimed at investigating the behaviour
 405 of suction anchors in normally consolidated clay under simplified multidirectional loading
 406 scenarios. These tests served as a proof of concept for a newly developed experimental setup

407 designed to apply controlled inclined loads from multiple mooring lines, as a step toward more
408 realistic simulations of shared anchor systems for floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs). The
409 main objective was to assess the functionality and performance of a newly developed
410 experimental setup capable of applying controlled inclined loads from multiple mooring lines.

411 Key findings include:

412 The experimental setup successfully enabled the application of controlled multidirectional
413 loading through an anchor design incorporating multiple padeyes. The load control system
414 performed consistently according to predefined load sequences. The combined use of laser
415 displacement sensors and DIC demonstrates the potential to monitor more complex load paths,
416 including realistic time histories and cyclic loading, confirming the setup's suitability for advanced
417 testing campaigns.

418 The monotonic inclined load test on Anchor 1 established a baseline ultimate capacity of
419 approximately 4 MN, serving as a reference for evaluating subsequent multi-directional load
420 responses.

421 Anchor 2, subjected to alternating loads from three mooring lines, showed progressive
422 accumulation of downward displacement. The final monotonic pull demonstrated a capacity
423 reduction of approximately 10% compared to the baseline, suggesting that load history and
424 directionality influence anchor response.

425 Anchor 3, tested under simultaneous two-line loading, exhibited greater horizontal and
426 upward displacements than Anchor 2. The increased load magnitude and steeper inclination
427 angle (average 63°) led to a final monotonic capacity reduction of approximately 38% relative to
428 Anchor 1, indicating a more pronounced degradation in holding capacity under the bidirectional
429 load paths applied.

430 Negative excess pore pressures were consistently mobilised near both the anchor base
431 and top, confirming 'suction resistance' (reverse end bearing) mobilisation. However, this effect
432 progressively diminished with repeated bidirectional loading, likely due to accumulated uplift
433 displacements compromising the anchor's sealing capacity and reducing its ability to generate
434 suction pressures.

435 Digital image correlation (DIC) successfully tracked anchor displacements in the
436 horizontal plane and showed good agreement with laser displacement measurements. The

437 analysis revealed more extensive horizontal displacement patterns of the anchor subjected to
438 bidirectional loading. The current setup could be enhanced with multicamera systems to better
439 capture three-dimensional anchor movement, including rotation.

440 Overall, this study provides a validated experimental setup and benchmark dataset for
441 future investigations into suction anchor behaviour under complex loading paths. While the
442 current experiments focused on simplified monotonic scenarios, the system is designed to support
443 further testing under fully cyclic and time-dependent loading conditions. The results offer a
444 foundation for the development and calibration of numerical models to support the design of
445 shared anchoring systems for floating offshore wind.

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567
568

569 **Figure Captions**

- 570 Figure 1. Target pre-consolidation pressures to build a normally consolidated clay profile (right
571 axis in prototype scale)
- 572 Figure 2. Plan view of the experimental setup: location of the suction anchors
- 573 Figure 3. Experimental setup for multiline anchor testing. a) Perspective view of the model
574 container and actuators. b) Detailed view of an anchor and instrumentation.
- 575 Figure 4. Rotating assembly to test various anchor locations
- 576 Figure 5. a) Detail of a model anchor; b) guide mechanism for installation; c) anchor installation
577 at 1-g
- 578 Figure 6. A view of a model anchor and instrumentation after installation at 1-g
- 579 Figure 7. Model instrumentation. a) Lateral view of an anchor and connection of one mooring
580 line. b) Linear lasers position to track lateral displacements. c) Point lasers to track vertical
581 displacements and detail of an ArUco marker
- 582 Figure 8. Anchor 2: progressively increasing amplitude monotonic loads applied by alternating
583 mooring lines
- 584 Figure 9. Anchor 3: progressively increasing amplitude monotonic loads applied by two mooring
585 lines simultaneously.
- 586 Figure 10. Undrained shear strength profiles measured in-flight and 1-g shear hand vane tests
- 587 Figure 11. Anchor 1: load-displacement response and excess pore pressure measurements at
588 the top and at the base of the anchor

589 Figure 12. Anchor 2: Load displacement curves for each mooring line
590 Figure 13. Anchor 2: Relationship between applied load and average vertical displacements
591 Figure 14. Anchor 2: alternated monotonic load with increasing magnitude, excess pore
592 pressures and vertical displacements response
593 Figure 15. Anchor 3: Resultant force- displacement curves for simultaneous loads applied by
594 two mooring lines simultaneously
595 Figure 16. Anchor 2: Relationship between applied load and average vertical displacements
596 Figure 17. Anchor 3: alternated monotonic load by two simultaneous mooring lines with
597 increasing magnitude, excess pore pressures and vertical displacements response
598 Figure 18. Trajectory of the ArUco marker, placed on the extension piece during anchor 2 and
599 anchor 3 tests
600 Figure 19. Horizontal–vertical (H–V) failure envelope with comparison to the load responses
601 from Anchors 1 to 3
602
603 **Table Captions**
604 Table 1. Prototype and model dimensions
605 Table 2. Identification of loading tests for the suction anchors